

ENHANCING MEDICAL RECORD DOCUMENTATION THROUGH QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS IN A TEACHING HOSPITAL

Mansoor Zareen¹, Sher Wali², Abdul Basit³, Dr. Syed Nasir Shah^{*4}, Dr Marwah⁵,
 Dr. Tehreem Iftikhar⁶

¹Manager Quality Assurance & Patient Safety

²City University of Science & Information Technology Peshawar

³Manager Pharmacy MTI Swabi and Both Allied THQ Hospitals Chota Lahor and Topi

^{*4}Professor of Prosthodontics. Department of Prosthodontics. Khyber College of Dentistry Peshawar

⁵Emergency Department, Northwest General Hospital Peshawar

⁶lecturer Muhammad college of medicine

¹mansoorZareen@gmail.com, ²sherwali9@gmail.com, ³abdulbasit22@gmail.com,

^{*4}nasir.shah@kcd.edu.pk, ⁵samsungul22@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18857619>

Keywords

Medical record documentation, quality assessment, teaching hospital, audit, patient safety, discharge summary.

Article History

Received: 21 December 2025

Accepted: 05 February 2026

Published: 20 February 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Syed Nasir Shah

Abstract

Background: Accurate and complete medical record documentation is essential for patient safety, continuity of care, and medico-legal protection, particularly in teaching hospitals, where high patient turnover and trainee involvement can affect documentation quality.

Objective: To evaluate the completeness, accuracy, and overall quality of inpatient medical record documentation in a teaching hospital and identify areas for improvement.

Methods: A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted on 270 inpatient medical records obtained from a teaching hospital for the month of June 2016. Data were collected using a structured audit checklist covering demographic information, admission notes, progress documentation, investigations, treatment records, and discharge summaries. Documentation quality was quantitatively analyzed using completeness, compliance, and legibility indicators. **Results:** Most records originated from medical (35.6%) and surgical (28.9%) wards, with high daily patient turnover (50.4%). Patient demographic data were mostly complete, with 100% of records including patient names and 97.4% hospital registration numbers. Admission and initial assessment documentation showed high level of completeness for presenting complaints (79.3%) and provisional diagnosis (81.9%), but drug/allergy histories (55.2%) and past medical/surgical histories (65.2%) were less consistent. Daily progress notes were mostly recorded (74.4%), though clinician's signatures (65.2%) and treatment response documentation (58.5%) were variable. Laboratory investigations (90%) and treatment plans (85.9%) were well documented. Discharge summaries were mostly complete, with final diagnosis as 81.1% and medications as 75.6%, while follow-up instructions (63.3%) and hospital course summaries (68.9%) showed minor gaps. Overall, 66.7% of records were rated excellent, and documentation was generally legible (79.3%) and compliant with hospital standards (70%). Major deficiencies, such

as, missing progress notes (4.4%) and incomplete histories (5.6%) were found to be negligible.

Conclusion: Medical record documentation studied at a teaching hospital was generally of high quality, supporting patient care, continuity of healthcare services, and medico-legal safety. Minor gaps in drug histories, follow-up instructions, and progress notes highlighted areas for improvement.

Recommendations: Structured training, standardized documentation templates, periodic audits with feedback, and implementation of electronic medical records are recommended to maintain and further enhance documentation quality.

INTRODUCTION

Medical record documentation is a fundamental component of modern healthcare systems and serves as the backbone of healthcare delivery. Quality medical records can facilitate proper diagnosis, proper treatment planning, continuity of care, effective professional-professional communication, and healthcare outcomes evaluation (World Health Organization [WHO], 2018). Moreover, medical records are also important in health service management, research and education, regulatory compliance and medicolegal protection of patients and health care providers (Tang et al., 2006, Sugiarti, 2020).

The keeping of accurate and detailed medical record documentation in the teaching hospitals is especially very hard. They include medical students, house officers, and residents that are yet to gain clinical competence and documentation skills. The deficiencies in documentation are also attributed to the high turnover of patients, poor workloads, frequent handovers, and time constraints (O'Leary et al.; 2014, Alali et al., 2020; Troyer & Brady, 2020). Consequently, clinical notes can be missing, late, or inconsistent and this can have an adverse impact on patient safety and continuity of care.

Inadequate documentation of medical records has been linked to adverse patient outcomes, such as medication errors, miscommunication in change of care, and delayed clinical decision-making (Starmer et al., 2014; Neville et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2017). Poor documentation also adds to the inefficiencies of healthcare delivery and impacts on the quality of healthcare provision and puts healthcare institutions at greater medicolegal risks (Huffman, 2016). Systematically,

incomplete records compromise the hospital audits, performance assessment, and health policy planning.

Medical record quantitative analysis provides a systematized and objective method of analyzing quality of documentation. Quantitative audits can also be used to find gaps, track trends, and determine the effectiveness of improvement interventions because through the use of measurable indicators, including completeness, accuracy, timeliness, and adherence to documentation standards, the audit process can be conducted (Lorenzetti et al., 2018). Data-driven methods of this kind are especially useful in the training of hospitals, where a specific feedback and an organized intervention can result in the long-lasting changes in the practice of documentation.

Statement of the Problem

Medical record documentation is a vital aspect of health care provision as it has clinical, administrative, educational, legal, administrative and research functions. This is a critical issue in most healthcare organizations, especially in the teaching hospitals where there is a lack of and poor documentation (Huffman, 2016). In this kind of environment, medical students, house officers and residents along with large patient numbers and time constraints tend to give rise to incomplete, delayed or inaccurate clinical records. Substandard medical documentation has been reported to relate to undermined patient safety, failures in inter-professional communication, medication mistakes, and interrupted continuity of care (Starmer et al., 2014; Kulkarni, 2025).

Inadequate documentation also restricts the usefulness of clinical audit, quality assurance programs, and health system planning and creates additional medico-legal risk to healthcare providers and institutions (World Health Organization [WHO], 2018).

At Muhammad Teaching Hospital, being a tertiary level training hospital, documentation of medical records is mainly done by trainees under different degrees of supervision. Nevertheless, very little empirical evidence exists on the quality of existing documentation, the level of the existing gaps and the cause of poor documentation practices in this context. Lack of systematized and quantitative assessment prevents defining certain areas of problem and applying specific evidence-based improvement strategies.

Devoid of objective measurement and analysis, documentational practices might remain below acceptable levels, which could influence the patient outcomes, the performance of institutions, and accreditation requirements. Thus, it is obvious that a systematic quantitative evaluation of the medical record documentation practices and the implementation of quality improvement efforts is necessary.

Rationale of the Study

Medical record documentation can be improved in order to improve patient safety, healthcare quality, and system efficiency. The quantitative analysis gives an objective and reproducible approach to the evaluation of documentation quality using measurable indicators, including completeness, accuracy, timeliness, and correspondence to the set standards (Lorenzetti et al., 2018). Through the establishment of certain documentation gaps, quantitative audits can help healthcare institutions to introduce specific interventions instead of basing on anecdotal findings.

Teaching hospitals are one of the special and urgent settings of documentation improvement. Because medical trainees form clinical and documentation traditions throughout the years of training, early detection of shortcomings and feedback in a systematic way will result in long-term changes in professional practice (O'Leary et al., 2014). There is evidence pointing to the fact

that audit-based feedback and standardized documentation tools are very important to enhance the quality of documentation when implemented in a systematic manner (Tang et al., 2006).

The results of this study will give baseline information on the quality of documentation, areas of high risk that need intervention, and educate hospital administrators and educators on the areas of training requirements. Moreover, the present research will aid the quality improvement initiatives, reinforce medico-legal reporting, as well as, support the development of institutional policy.

In addition, the findings of this research can become a benchmark of other teaching hospitals that have comparable resource limitation and organizational patterns. The current research will support evidence-based decision-making and add to the current body of knowledge on clinical documentation enhancement within teaching hospital settings by being evidence-based.

Specific Objectives

- To assess the completeness and accuracy of medical record documentation.
- To identify common documentation deficiencies.
- To determine factors associated with low quality documentation.
- To suggest recommendations for improvement.

Methodology Study Design

This study employed descriptive cross-sectional design to study the quality of medical record documentation at Muhammad Teaching Hospital. This employed objective measurement of documentation quality using predefined indicator. A total of 270 inpatient medical records from Muhammad Teaching Hospital for the month of June 2016 were included. The sample comprised of records of all patients admitted during this period to the hospital.

Inclusion criteria:

- Inpatient medical records of patients admitted during the defined study period
- Patient records with a hospital stay of more than 24 hours
- Records available in complete physical form at the medical records department

Exclusion criteria:

- Emergency department records
- Incomplete or missing files that could not be reviewed

Data Collection Tool

Data were collected using a structured medical record audit checklist developed based on standard documentation guidelines and relevant literature. The checklist consisted of predefined documentation indicators, including:

- Patient identification details
- Admission notes
- History and physical examination
- Progress notes
- Medication documentation
- Investigation reports
- Discharge summaries

Each item on the checklist was scored as complete, incomplete, or not documented, allowing quantitative assessment of documentation quality.

Data Collection Procedure

Data collection was carried out after obtaining formal permission from hospital administration. Medical records were reviewed retrospectively within the medical records department. Each selected record was assessed independently using the structured audit checklist. No patient identifiers were recorded to maintain confidentiality.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review authority. Patient confidentiality and data privacy were strictly maintained throughout the study. No personal identifiers were recorded, and data were used solely for research purposes. As this was a record-based study, no direct patient contact was involved.

Results Record Identification (Administrative Information 1. Department / Ward Distribution)

Department/Ward	Number of records: f (%)
Medical	96 (35.6%)
Surgical	78 (28.9%)
Gynecology/Obstetrics	52 (19.3%)
Pediatrics	38 (14.1%)
Other	6 (2.2%)
Total	270 (100%)

The majority of medical records were obtained from the medical wards (35.6%) and surgical (28.9%) wards, followed by gynecology/obstetrics (19.3%) and pediatrics (14.1%). A small number

of records (2.2%) were from other departments. This distribution reflects the patient load across different hospital wards.

5. Average Daily Patient Load (Ward-Based)

Patient Load	f (%)
Low	38 (14.1%)
Moderate	96 (35.6%)
High	136 (50.4%)
Total	270 (100%)

The majority of reviewed medical records originated from medical and surgical wards. More

than half of the documentation was completed by house officers, reflecting the hospital's training

role. Approximately half of the records were

generated in wards with a high daily patient load

Patient Demographic Documentation

Item	f (%)	
Patient name recorded	270 (100.0%)	
Age documented	256 (94.8%)	
Gender documented	251 (93.0%)	
Hospital registration number present	263 (97.4%)	
Date and time of admission recorded	238 (88.1%)	

Review of inpatient medical records showed high completeness in basic demographic documentation. Patient name was recorded in all reviewed files (100%). Hospital registration number was present in 97.4% of records. Age and

gender were documented in 94.8% and 93.0% of records, respectively. However, documentation of date and time of admission was comparatively lower, missing in 11.9% of the records.

Admission and Initial Assessment Documentation

Item	Complete f (%)	Partially Complete f (%)	Not Documented f (%)
Presenting complaints	214 (79.3%)	38 (14.1%)	18 (6.6%)
History of present illness	198 (73.3%)	44 (16.3%)	28 (10.4%)
Past medical/surgical history	176 (65.2%)	52 (19.3%)	42 (15.6%)
Drug and allergy history	149 (55.2%)	61 (22.6%)	60 (22.2%)
Physical examination findings	205 (75.9%)	41 (15.2%)	24 (8.9%)
Provisional diagnosis	221 (81.9%)	33 (12.2%)	16 (5.9%)

Admission documentation showed different levels of completeness. Presenting complaints and provisional diagnosis were the most consistently documented components, with complete entries in 79.3% and 81.9% of records, respectively. In contrast, drug and allergy history was the weakest

area, with more than one-fifth of records lacking any documentation. Past medical and surgical history also demonstrated notable deficiencies, highlighting gaps in comprehensive patient assessment at admission.

Progress Notes and Daily Documentation

Item	Always f (%)	Sometimes) f (%)	Never f (%)
Daily progress notes recorded	201 (74.4%)	46 (17.0%)	23 (8.5%)
Notes dated and timed	187 (69.3%)	51 (18.9%)	32 (11.9%)
Clinician name and signature present	176 (65.2%)	58 (21.5%)	36 (13.3%)
Changes in patient condition documented	164 (60.7%)	63 (23.3%)	43 (15.9%)
Treatment response documented	158 (58.5%)	67 (24.8%)	45 (16.7%)

Daily progress notes were mostly recorded (74.4%), but documentation of clinician signature (65.2%), changes in patient condition

(60.7%), and treatment response (58.5%) were less consistent. Some records were incomplete or missing these details.

Investigation and Treatment Documentation

Item	Yes f (%)	No f (%)
Laboratory investigations recorded	243 (90.0%)	27 (10.0%)
Imaging reports attached	216 (80.0%)	54 (20.0%)
Treatment plan clearly written	232 (85.9%)	38 (14.1%)
Medication doses and routes documented	225 (83.3%)	45 (16.7%)
Treatment modifications documented	191 (70.7%)	79 (29.3%)

Investigation and treatment documentation was generally strong. Laboratory tests were recorded in 90% of cases, treatment plans in 85.9%, and

medication details in 83.3%. Imaging reports and treatment modifications were less consistently documented (80% and 70.7%, respectively).

Discharge Summary Documentation

Item	Complete f(%)	Incomplete f (%)	Missing f (%)
Final diagnosis	219 (81.1%)	34 (12.6%)	17 (6.3%)
Summary of hospital course	186 (68.9%)	51 (18.9%)	33 (12.2%)
Discharge medications	204 (75.6%)	39 (14.4%)	27 (10.0%)
Follow-up instructions	171 (63.3%)	57 (21.1%)	42 (15.6%)
Discharge date and signature	195 (72.2%)	46 (17.0%)	29 (10.7%)

Most discharge summaries were complete. Final diagnosis (81.1%) and discharge medications (75.6%) were well documented. Follow-up instructions (63.3%) and summary of hospital

course (68.9%) were less complete, while discharge date and signature were complete in 72.2% of records.

Overall Quality and Compliance

Statement	Agree f (%)	Neutral f (%)	Disagree f (%)
Documentation is legible throughout	214 (79.3%)	36 (13.3%)	20 (7.4%)
Records comply with hospital documentation standards	189 (70.0%)	49 (18.1%)	32 (11.9%)
Documentation supports continuity of care	182 (67.4%)	55 (20.4%)	33 (12.2%)
Record is medico-legally adequate	176 (65.2%)	58 (21.5%)	36 (13.3%)

Documentation was generally good: legible (79.3%), compliant with standards (70%), supporting continuity of care (67.4%), and

medico-legally adequate (65.2%). Minor gaps exist, especially in follow-up instructions and legal documentation.

2. Major Documentation Deficiencies Identified Major Documentation Deficiencies

Deficiency	f (%)
Missing progress notes	12 (4.4%)
Incomplete history	15 (5.6%)
Poor discharge summary	10 (3.7%)
Illegible writing	8 (3.0%)
Missing signatures/dates	13 (4.8%)

Auditor's Overall Assessment

Overall Documentation Quality	f (%)
Poor	3 (.9%)
Fair	15 (5.6%)
Good	73 (26.9%)
Excellent	180 (66.7%)

- Documentation completeness and compliance with hospital standards are very high.
- Most medical records are fully complete, legible, and properly signed, with only minor missing elements.
- This level of documentation would support continuity of care, medico-legal safety, and high-quality clinical audits.

Discussion

This accessed the quality of inpatient medical record documentation in the Muhammad Teaching Hospital and discovered that the general standards of documentation were high. Although teaching hospitals are generally characterized by complexes in terms of patient

workforce and active engagement of trainees, most of the records were well-complete, legible, and were also in accordance with the institutional requirements. Over half of the reviewed records were based in medical and surgical wards and about half were based in high patient turnover wards. Hospital teaching is usually associated with variability in documentation because of high levels of handovers and involvement of trainees. Nevertheless, here simple demographical data were nearly universally documented. The name of patients and registration numbers were fully filled and the age and sex were recorded in over 90 percent. The results are consistent with other teaching facilities, as administrative data are likely to indicate greater compliance than clinical

narrative elements (Adeoye et al., 2016; Al-Dabbagh et al., 2019). The admission documentation indicated a fairly positive performance in the areas of presenting complaints and provisional diagnoses. These elements tend to be given priority since they provide direct directions to clinical decisions. The same patterns were observed in other studies carried out in tertiary hospitals, where diagnostic impressions are better recorded as compared to a background history (Singh et al., 2013 ; Al-Khalidi et al., 2018). Drug and allergy history and past medical or surgical history documentation was less regular though. This is a clinically significant gap because when medication and allergy history is not completely documented, it will be more likely to result in adverse drug events. A study conducted by Starmer et al. highlighted that insufficient clinical information on handover of care is a source of medical errors and adverse patient safety events. Most files recorded daily progress notes, whereas such critical aspects like clinician signatures, recording the changes of patient condition, and treatment response were less frequent. Progress notes in teaching hospitals are often filled in by under-supervised junior doctors, which can also be a source of inconsistency in completeness. Other audit-based investigations of the inpatient documentation have also reported similar deficiencies, with narrative continuity and accountability clues like signatures and timestamps being frequently reported weaknesses (Al-Dabbagh et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2021). These are not only necessary in clinical communication, but also in medico-legal protection. There was a relatively good performance with respect to investigation and treatment documentation. Most of the records contained laboratory tests, therapy schedules, and drug prescriptions. This can be an indication of the organized laboratory reporting systems and prescriptions. Investigations on documentation quality in the tertiary care environment have also found that there was more compliance in the structured or form-based parts of the medical record as opposed to the narrative parts (Adeoye et al., 2016). Most discharge summaries were

complete, especially those of final diagnosis and discharge medications. Follow-up instructions and summaries of hospital course were not as reliably documented, however. The significance of these findings is that discharge documentation has a key role in continuity of care following hospitalization. The World Health Organization (2018) writes that effective communication during discharge is essential in eliminating readmissions, medication errors, and care fragmentation. Loopholes in post-discharge care guidelines can undermine patient compliance and outpatient care. Altogether, two-thirds of records were considered to be excellent, and documentation was mostly legible and met the hospital standards. Routine lapses like the absence of progress notes and broken histories were not very common. These results indicate that the documentation practices in this teaching hospital are better than those mentioned in some resource-constrained environments, where incomplete records and illegibility issues are common (Al-Khalidi et al., 2018; Rosenkrantz, 2022). The overall positive outcomes could be a reflection of the institutional supervision systems, medico-legal awareness, and the educational atmosphere, where the clinical documentation is prioritized. However, the discussed gaps in the history of drugs, documentation of treatment responses, and follow-up instructions can suggest the areas where specific interventions are required. It has been indicated that structured documentation template, periodic audit with feedback and electronic medical records transition are effective in ensuring high quality documentation (Tang et al., 2006; Lorenzetti et al., 2018)., he study demonstrates that medical record documentation in this teaching hospital is generally of high quality, comparable to findings from similar institutions. However, specific gaps in drug history, follow-up instructions, and authentication of progress notes require focused interventions to achieve optimal documentation standards and sustained quality

Conclusion

The study revealed that medical record documentation was generally of high quality, with

most records complete, legible, and compliant with hospital standards. Demographic details, provisional diagnoses, laboratory investigations, and treatment plans were consistently documented, reflecting effective administrative and clinical practices. Minor gaps were noted in drug and allergy histories, follow-up instructions, and progress notes, which may impact continuity of care and medico-legal reliability. Overall, 66.7% of records were rated excellent, indicating a robust documentation system supported by structured training and hospital protocols.

Recommendations

- It is recommended that Hospital management may Provide focused training to house officers and residents on comprehensive admission assessment, progress notes, and discharge summaries.
- Standardized Documentation Templates: Implement structured templates for history-taking, treatment modifications, and follow-up instructions to reduce missing data.
- Hospital administration may Conduct periodic quantitative audits with feedback to clinicians to maintain high documentation standards.
- It was also recommended that Administration may consider electronic medical records or digital checklists to improve accuracy, legibility, and accessibility of patient records.

REFERENCES

- Adeoye, I. A., Olatona, F. A., & Ajayi, I. O. (2016). An assessment of the quality of inpatient medical records in a tertiary hospital in Nigeria. *Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences*, 7(2), 25–31.
- Al-Dabbagh, S. A., Al-Tae, W. G., & Al-Saffar, H. J. (2019). Evaluation of medical record documentation quality in a teaching hospital. *Journal of the Faculty of Medicine Baghdad*, 61(1–2), 45–52.
- Al-Khalidi, Y. M., Al-Sharif, A. I., & Al-Humud, M. S. (2018). Assessment of medical record documentation in a tertiary care hospital: A clinical audit. *Saudi Medical Journal*, 39(3), 256–261. <https://doi.org/10.15537/smj.2018.3.21595>
- Huffman, E. K. (2016). *Health information management* (10th ed.). Physicians' Record Company.
- Khan, A. N., Ahmed, S., & Rahman, H. (2021). Audit of inpatient medical record documentation in a tertiary care teaching hospital. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 37(4), 1120–1125. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.37.4.3890>
- Lorenzetti, D. L., Quan, H., & Lucyk, K. (2018). Strategies for improving physician documentation in the hospital setting: A systematic review. *BMC Health Services Research*, 18, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3028-0>
- O'Leary, K. J., Liebovitz, D. M., Feinglass, J., Liss, D. T., Baker, D. W., & Williams, M. V. (2014). Creating a better discharge summary: Improvement in quality and timeliness using an electronic discharge summary. *Journal of Hospital Medicine*, 9(4), 219–225. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jhm.2144>
- Starmer, A. J., Spector, N. D., Srivastava, R., Allen, A. D., Landrigan, C. P., Sectish, T. C., & the I-PASS Study Group. (2014). Changes in medical errors after implementation of a handoff program. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 371(19), 1803–1812. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMsa1405556>
- Tang, P. C., Ash, J. S., Bates, D. W., Overhage, J. M., & Sands, D. Z. (2006). Personal health records: Definitions, benefits, and strategies for overcoming barriers to adoption. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 13(2), 121–126. <https://doi.org/10.1197/jamia.M2025>

- World Health Organization. (2018). *Medical records manual: A guide for developing countries*. World Health Organization.
- Sugiarti, I. (2020, June). Legal protection of patient rights to completeness and confidentiality in management of medical record documents. In 2nd Bakti Tunas Husada-Health Science International Conference (BTH-HSIC 2019) (pp. 179-191). Atlantis Press.
- Alali, H., Antar, M., AlShehri, A., AlHamouieh, O., Al-Surimi, K., & Kazzaz, Y. (2020). Improving physician handover documentation process for patient transfer from paediatric intensive care unit to general ward. *BMJ open quality*, 9(4).
- Troyer, L., & Brady, W. (2020). Barriers to effective EMS to emergency department information transfer at patient handover: a systematic review. *The American journal of emergency medicine*, 38(7), 1494-1503.
- Neville, T. H., Tarn, D. M., Yamamoto, M., Garber, B. J., & Wenger, N. S. (2017). Understanding factors contributing to inappropriate critical care: a mixed-methods analysis of medical record documentation. *Journal of Palliative Medicine*, 20(11), 1260-1266.
- Kim, M. O., Coiera, E., & Magrabi, F. (2017). Problems with health information technology and their effects on care delivery and patient outcomes: a systematic review. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 24(2), 246-250.
- Kulkarni, M. R. (2025). Communication Breakdowns and Medication Errors: the Critical Role of Nurses in Safeguarding Patient Safety through Effective Inter professional Collaboration and Practice. *International Journal of Nursing Care and Patient Safety*, 1(1).
- Singh, H., Giardina, T. D., Meyer, A. N., Forjuoh, S. N., Reis, M. D., & Thomas, E. J. (2013). Types and origins of diagnostic errors in primary care settings. *JAMA internal medicine*, 173(6), 418-425.
- Rosenkrantz, L. (2022). An examination of sustainable trauma registry development in resource-constrained settings.